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LSTM vs CNN in real ship trajectory classification

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Abstract. Ship type identification in a maritime context can be critical to the authorities to control the activities being carried out. Although Automatic Identification Systems has been mandatory for certain vessels if a vessel does not have them voluntarily or not, it can lead to a whole set of problems, so the use of tracking alternatives such as radar is fully complementary for a vessel monitoring systems. However, radars provide positions, but not what they are detecting. Having systems capable of adding categorical information to radar detections of vessels makes it possible to increase control of the activities being carried out, improve safety in maritime traffic, and optimize on-site inspection resources on the part of the authorities. This paper addresses the binary classification problem (fishing ships versus all other vessels) using unbalanced data from real vessel trajectories. It is performed from a Deep Learning approach comparing two of the main trends, Convolutional Neural Networks and Long Short-Term Memory. In this paper, it is proposed the weighted Cross-Entropy methodology and compared with classical data balancing strategies. Both networks show high performance when applying weighted Cross-Entropy compared to the classical machine learning approaches and classical balancing techniques. This work is shown to be a novel approach to the international problem of identifying fishing ships without context.

Keywords: Deep Learning, LSTM, CNN, Weighted Cross Entropy, Automatic Identification System, Fishing ship classification.

1 Introduction

Although the problem of Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated Fishing (IUU-Fishing) is not new [1], it continues to be a topical issue in international relationships [2, 3].

As the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) shows in [4], yearly in the world IUU-fishing extract around 26 million tonnes of seafood. Recent studies, such as that of U.R.Sumalia et al. [5], estimated between 8 and 14 million metric tons of unreported catches estimating financing of the illegal fishing market of US\$9 billion to US\$17 billion in the world. In addition, the study estimates the annual economic impact and the loss of tax revenue for the countries between US\$2 and US\$4 billion, showing a table with the detailed data.

Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS) and Automatic Identification Systems (AIS) are powerful tools for authorities to address legislative challenges as IUU- fishing. Any

VMS requires technology on the vessel, onshore, and communication between them. Specifically, AIS systems provide real-time vessel type and position information. All other ships in turn can know the positions of their nearest neighbors.

Although these systems are mandatory, the use of radars is essential for a robust and functional VMS. Unlike the GPS systems associated with vessels, radars only provide the position of objects in the detection range, so they cannot differentiate the type of vessel. Having systems capable of extracting context information related to the trajectories that these systems can identify is of particular interest not only to improve the accuracy of VMS systems but also to identify irregularities in maritime traffic, to identify illegal activities, or even for rescue work.

In this paper we address the problem of vessel classification based on trajectories. Specifically, the binary classification of fishing ships trajectories versus other ships, studying the performance provided by two trendy deep learning (DL) approaches. These approaches transform the classification problem into a data learning problem. This learning problem is base to adjust the internal neural network parameters, so the low-level problem is translated into an optimization problem. To address the learning problem associated with approximations with highly unbalanced real-world data, we propose to use weights in the cost function during the learning phase and compare the performance with other classical techniques.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 shows the related works. Section 3 describes the methodology describing the data set, validation strategies, classification models and the learning problem. Experimental results are shown in Section 4. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section 5.

2 Related works

In D. Sánchez et al. [6] authors focus on feature extraction of vessel trajectories from the Danish Coastal getting from the AIS system [7]. The authors propose a data preprocessing methodology that they validate using a set of classical machine learning (ML) approximation classifiers to solve the binary problem of fishing ships versus other vessels. These approximations show high sensitivity to the bias of the data in the proposed binary problem. The authors introduce the problem unbalanced data and evaluate the performance of classifiers applying different subprocesses including two balancing methods, Random Undersampling (RUS) [8] and Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) [9]. Other researches such as [10, 11] also focus on the classification of fishing ships with classical approaches and searching features to describe vessel trajectories. However, these approaches seem to have reached an impasse as can be seen in [6], so use other approaches with high results in other fields such as Deep Learning (DL) is justified.

From the DL classification approach, there are two main branches. The first one uses a Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [12, 13] and the second one uses Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM) [14, 15]. The previous works focus in one of the two branches, nonetheless a comparison between the two trends on the same problem can yield interesting solutions. For example, in estimation problems related to ships trajectories we can find comparisons between LSTM and CNN solutions. In [16] three solutions with CNN, LSTM and a hybridization between both, BDLSTM-CNN, are

compared for the estimation of the maritime vessel flow. In this research the LSTM architecture has a lower Error Rate than CNN but both are improved by the BDLSTM-CNN proposal in the prediction problem over 4 time steps.

The features used to define the flow are limited to the spatial grid of the study, being a bounded solution to the case study.

CNNs in classification problems have two principal steps, feature extraction (convolutional phases) and classification. These approaches have proven to be one of the most accurate techniques in multiclass problems due to their ability to learn relevant classification features. CNN architectures require a fixed input structure, for example, an image or in the case of trajectories a fixed time window. LSTM models are widely used with sequential data, mainly in non-Markovian systems such as natural language processing [17] or human behavior [18]. This is because their long-term memory properties allow remembering past trends of the states, understanding as state the temporal input variables to the network. Generally, DL-based classification systems use cross-entropy [19] as a cost function to optimize the internal network parameters. Related work on real-world data such as [20, 21] proposes the use of weights associated with classes to improve learning and avoid classification bias. This technique is known as Weighted Cross-Entropy (WCE). The research of Y. Sousa et al. [20] propose a new approach called CSEFMLP (Cost-Sensitive Cross-Entropy Error Function for MLP neural networks) based on the cross-entropy radius to weight the weights of the cross-entropy. This radius evaluates the contribution of each class on the cost function. The authors compare the performance of the proposal with other common balancing-classification techniques for different unbalanced databases. They finally conclude that the performance generally improves or at least similarly the performance of other strategies. In the work of M.R. Rezaei et al. [21] a binary classification problem with the Inception-V3 network is presented in which different increasing values of weights associated to the cost function are compared under usual classification metrics. WCE assigns more weight to the minority class, penalizing more incorrect predictions, and thus enabling better and faster training for the minority class. Research such as that of Shen Lu et al. [22] proposes a dynamic weighting cross-entropy technique for semantic segmentation. In this type of WCE the value of the weights changes as the background is differentiated from the non-background. Their research shows the use of the proposed WCE method improves the degradation from the extremely unbalanced data. In recent studies such as [23] or J.P.Llerena et al. [24] authors used LSTM networks for state-space estimation and filtering in highly nonlinear systems. These studies show the LSTM learning capacity in complex environments. It also shows the possibilities of using Sequence-to-sequence architectures that allow step-by-step estimation opening the possibilities to classify step-by-step temporal sequences or trajectories.

3 Methodology

In this paper, we propose to compare the two principal deep learning approach trends in literature, CNN, and LSTM architectures, to classify an extremely imbalanced data problem and find the contribution to use WCE in relation to other balance techniques. Specifically, this paper use kinematics features from trajectories of two classes of vessels (fishing ships and other ships). For this purpose, the methodology section first

describes the database, its structure, and partitioning for the learning problem with two different validation strategies. Then we briefly describe the classical approach model that we will use as comparison. Finally, this section is concluded with the proposed neural network architectures used and the justification for the weight selection proposal method in the NN-learning problem.

3.1 Real world binary dataset

We use trajectories of AIS-recorded ships off the coast of Denmark [7] preprocessed according to [6]. Each AIS raw trajectory is defined as a succession of spatial positions and a sampling time. This research explains in detail the data preprocessing and the set of references on which they are based to finally extract the kinematic states of the vessels. In addition, the segmentation of the resulting trajectories is justified, and finally, a set of trajectories defined by continuous segments of 50 samples, normalized 10-feature space and N elements. In this work, we start from this data structure provided by its authors. Specifically, the database Φ is structured for a learning problem $\Phi = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} | i = 1, \dots, N\}$ where the tensor features $\mathbf{x}_i^1 = \{t, p_{x,y}, v_{x,y}, \Delta v, |v_{x,y}|, d, \Delta\psi, \Delta t\}$, building a data panel of 10 features and 50 samples, $\mathbf{x}^1 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 10 \times 50}$, superscript one over x means first data structure. Where t is the normalized sample times, $p_{x,y}$ is the normalization position component, $v_{x,y}$ speed components, Δv is the speed variation, $|v_{x,y}|$ is the speed vector modulus, d is the distance inter-samples, $\Delta\psi$ is the direction variation, and the end Δt is the time gap. In order to flatten the data panel \mathbf{x}_i^1 , to be applied in classifiers with a flattened fixed input, we generate a flatten vector as [6] composed of normalization total time and five main blocks. In addition to the statistical characteristics of [6], the sum value is included in each feature block. Specifically,

$\mathbf{x}_i^2 = \{T, \text{Time}, \text{speed}, \text{distance}, \text{Course variation}, \text{speed variation}, \text{time gaps}\}$. Each block composes by sum, mean, max, min, standard deviation, mode, and three quartiles, from each feature from the previous panel data \mathbf{x}_i^1 , getting a vector of 46 static characteristics for each trajectory, were $\mathbf{x}^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 46 \times 1}$. In this way, we define the trajectory i of vessel y_i , in two different ways, \mathbf{x}_i^1 and \mathbf{x}_i^2 . So, we use two learning sets $\Phi_1 = \{(\mathbf{x}_i^1, y_i) \in \mathcal{X}^1 \times \mathcal{Y} | i = 1, \dots, N\}$ and $\Phi_2 = \{(\mathbf{x}_i^2, y_i) \in \mathcal{X}^2 \times \mathcal{Y} | i = 1, \dots, N\}$. Being $N=118884$, the number of trajectories. Although the AIS system can differentiate a total of 18 different classes of vessels, in this paper we focus on the fishing class as opposed to the rest, in other words, two different classes $\{A, B\}$, fishing ships, and other ship types respectively. Associating to each sample the class A or B we obtain that $N_A = 22495$ and $N_B = 96389$, where it is easily observed that the classes are unbalanced **Fig. 1** and propagated for training and validation. While in a balanced set the samples would be split 50/50, in our case the samples are split 81.1% for B and 18.9% for A.

Data for validation methodologies

In this paper we use two of the main techniques for validation models Holdout and stratified K-fold. To apply each of these methodologies, the database is divided differently. For the holdout case the database is divided into two parts with random data selection, training, and test. Specifically, 70% of the data is selected for training and the remaining 30% for validation $N = \{N_{70\%}, N_{30\%}\} = \{83218, 35666\}$. **Fig. 1** (a)

shows the distribution of training and test data. The number of trajectories per class in holdout partition is $N_A = \{15746, 6749\}$ and $N_B = \{67472, 28917\}$. On the other hand, to apply K-fold validation, the dataset is divided into K packages (folds) similar than holdout structure (training and test).

Fig. 1. Data partition to validation methodology. (a) Holdout partition. Blue training data, brown validation data. (b) K-Fold stratified partition set.

The selection of the data for the K-folds is done randomly but keeping the same proportion by classes as in the starting set. This type of selection is called K-Fold stratified and show in **Fig. 1** (b). A fair amount of research has focused on the empirical performance of cross-validation. In R. Bharat Rao and Glenn Funng [25] research different studies are discussed where it seems to have been agreed that a value of $k=10$ usually shows good bias-variance compensation results for classifiers. In addition, Sánchez et al. [6] authors include a K-Fold section where they use 10 folds. Based on previous research in this paper we use 10-folds. Each fold training-test set has $N_A = \{20245, 2250\}$ and $N_B = \{86750, 9639\}$ trajectories per class. In both cases of **Fig. 1**, the different numbers of trajectories per class show an imbalanced distribution.

3.2 Classical approach

A first attempt to differentiate fishing ships from other ships using features extracted from vessel trajectories is to use the classical decision tree algorithm. The algorithm is integrated into the MATLAB Machine Learning Toolbox [26], based on the classic text of Leo Breiman et al. [27]. This method requires a flattened vector $\mathbf{x}^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 46 \times 1}$ with fixed input features, so it uses the preprocessed set Φ_2 described in section 3.1.

3.3 Deep Learning approach

Since the features extracted from the trajectories can be expressed in a temporal way Φ_1 and in a static way Φ_2 , we propose to address the problem with the most common DL trends in the literature, LSTM, and CNN networks. Both proposals share the Soft-Max output layer and cross-entropy cost function [19]. Thus, the classification problem becomes a biased learning problem.

CNN classifier structure.

The CNN structure is inspired by the feature extraction stage in the architecture proposed by [28] for speech command recognition and the famous AlexNet architecture [29] for the classification step. We generate two CNN networks that differ at the input layer. On the one hand, the first one addresses the static database with $46 \times 1 \times 1$ structure, while the second one uses the data panel with $10 \times 50 \times 1$ structure. Finally, the architecture is composed of an input layer, a convolutional module C, two consecutive fully connected layers with a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function of 4096 units and 30% dropout. The last block is composed of a fully connected layer with 2 units (binary classification) and a SoftMax layer.

Module C include 3 consecutive convolutional blocks. Each convolutional block is composed of four layers, convolution, batch normalization, activation, and pooling. The convolutional layer has 12, 24, and 48 filters respectively of 3×3 filter size, astride of 1×1 , and padding same to ensure the output has the same size as the input. Then a batch normalization layer follows of ReLU activation layer and pooling layer. The max pooling layer is composed of pool size 3×3 and stride 2×2 and padding same. In the case of temporary CNN, the last convolutional block is duplicated.

Fig. 2. CNN Architecture, first block: input layer. Second: convolutional deep feature extraction module. Third and fourth: Fully connected plus ReLU layer and dropout. Last two layers, fully connected layer and SoftMax layer.

It is used Adam optimizer [30] with an initial learning rate of $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and learning rate drop factor 0.09. The minimum batch size is 200 and 40 epochs. In the case of K-Fold each of the K-Folds is trained in the same way but with 15 epochs.

LSTM classifier structure.

In the case of the LSTM architecture, the network learns hidden transitions of the temporal sequences of the input features. The model used is employed in the work of [31] for fault detection in chemical processes, and can be seen represented in **Fig. 3**. The architecture is composed of a 10×50 sequence input layer, three consecutive LSTM layers with 20% dropout and 52, 40, and 25 hidden units respectively. Finally, a fully connected layer with two units and a classification SoftMax layer. The outputs of the first two LSTM layers are complete sequences, while in the case of the last LSTM layer only the last step sequence is selected to connect it to the fully connected layer.

Fig. 3. LSTM Architecture, first block input layer (sequence), second to fourth block LSTM layers with dropout. Last two layers, fully connected layer and SoftMax layer.

The training hyperparameters are optimizer Adam, minimum batch size 550. Gradient thresholding is applied with value 1 using the L_2 norm.

Learning problem

The main relation between CNN and LSTM approach lies in the output SoftMax layer and the cost function. Specifically, the typical cost function \mathcal{L} used in classification deep learning problems is cross-entropy, that compare two probability distribution over the same probability space.

Given a database $\Phi =$, in which each element i is described by a feature tensor x_i and has a $q_{i,k}$ probability of belonging to a categorical class k , designing an artificial neural network classifier $\hat{q}_{\theta}(x_i)_k$, involves identifying the internal NN θ parameters that minimize the error function \mathcal{L} (1).

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NN}}(\theta) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K w_k q_{i,k} \ln(\hat{q}_{\theta}(x_i)_k) \quad (1)$$

Where, K is the total number of classes, and N is the total number of samples.

The real probability of sample i belonging to class k are $q_{i,k}$ and $\hat{q}_{\theta}(x_i)_k$ the probability given by the prediction of the model/neural network with internal weights θ of sample i (with inputs x_i) belonging to class k . On the other hand, $q, \hat{q}: \mathbb{R}^K \rightarrow [0,1]^K$ and in the case of \hat{q} provided by the SoftMax function (2).

$$\hat{q}(z_i)_k = \frac{e^{z_{i,k}}}{\sum_{k=1}^K e^{z_{i,k}}} \quad (2)$$

Where $z_{i,k} = f_{\theta}(x_i)$ is the k element of the output vector at the network output function f_{θ} , before getting the SoftMax layer when introducing a x_i feature tensor. In other words, $f_{\theta}(x_i)$ is the NN function. We use the hat over q (\hat{q}) inherited from the estimator notation since the network provides an estimate while q tells us the true value of the database. w_k is the weight associated with class k . For the case of two classes A and B:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NN}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N w_A q_{i,A} \ln(\hat{q}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(x_i)_A) + w_B q_{i,B} \ln(\hat{q}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(x_i)_B) \quad (3)$$

Since the SoftMax function provides the probability of belonging to each A or B class, $\hat{q}_{i,A} + \hat{q}_{i,B} = 1$, and likewise the database probabilities satisfy the same relationship but in an unequivocal way $q_{i,B} = 1 - q_{i,A}$, $q_{i,k} \in \{1,0\}$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NN}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N w_A q_i \ln(\hat{q}_{i,\boldsymbol{\theta}}) + w_B (1 - q_i) \ln(1 - \hat{q}_{i,\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \quad (4)$$

The first term of the summation in equation (4), contributes to the error of the positive terms (fishing ships) while the second term contributes to the error of the negative terms (other vessels). If the database is balanced means $N_A = N_B = 0,5N$, the probability of element i belonging to the classes A or B is the same [20], in such that both terms will act the same number of times $q_{i,k} = \frac{N_k}{N} = \frac{1}{2}$. However, if the database is unbalanced, $q_{i,A} \neq q_{i,B}$ the majority subset will contribute more times in the error function than the minority subset. This effect over the cost function can be balanced by weights (w_k), were:

$$\begin{cases} N_A = N_B, w_A = w_B = 1 \\ N_A \ll N_B, w_A > 1 \text{ y } w_B < 1 \\ N_A \gg N_B, w_A < 1 \text{ y } w_B > 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In order to have the same contribution of each class over the error function $w_A q_{i,A} = w_B q_{i,B}$, $w_A = \frac{N_B}{N_A} w_B$. The previous relationship indicates that the weight associated with a class k must be inversely proportional to the number of samples N of that class. In addition, to maintain the definition of cross-entropy (1), the sum of the weights must be equal to the number of classes $\sum_{k=1}^K w_k = w_A + w_B = K = 2$. Based on these restrictions, we use (6).

$$w_k = \frac{1/N_k}{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K 1/N_k} = \frac{K}{N_k \sum_{k=1}^K 1/N_k} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 4 shows the contribution of the classifier error to the cross entropy to applied equation (6). When the database is balanced the effect of the classification error is similar in both classes. However, in our case the database is imbalanced with a ratio around to the 18,9% to the positive class and 21,9% for the negative class. With these relationships equation (6) gives the weights of **Fig. 4b**. This figure shows the error effect of the minority class, solid blue line, is stronger than the majority class, dashed red line.

Fig. 4. Contribution to cross-entropy with weight adjustment (6). Solid blue line, positive class, dashed red line, negative class. (a) Weights for balanced database. (b) Weights for unbalanced database.

4 Experiments and results

The experimentation seeks to evaluate the performance of the two proposed deep learning approaches to the same fishing ship classification problem, introducing as a novelty the WCE to solve the classification bias produced by the imbalance data. The classification methods are a decision tree, CNN, LSTM and CNN by fix time window over kinematics data that we call CNN_T. During the training phase, unbalanced raw features (Without B.), two classical balancing methods RUS and SMOTE and the WCE formulated in *Learning problem* section. We applied two validation strategies, holdout, and stratified K-Fold with $K = 10$. RUS and SMOTE balancing techniques are applied over each k-folds training sets, isolated synthetic disturbance validation folds or decimation data. The results are compared in \mathbb{R}^2 bounded space defined by accuracy (7) and F_1 -Score (9) metrics. The first metric indicates an overall accuracy of the positives, however in an unbalanced sample a classifier can show a very high accuracy without detecting some classes, so the classifier's will also be unbalanced. For this reason, we use the harmonic mean between precision and recall (8) called F_β -Score or F_1 . Where β is a weight indicating the importance, we give to precision versus recall, in our case the same ($\beta = 1$). The quantitative results are shown in **Table 1** and **Table 2**. The union of these two metrics forms a plane \mathbb{R}^2 of precision in which the ideal classifier would be at coordinates (1,1).

$$Acc = \frac{Tp + Tn}{Tp + Tn + Fp + Fn} \quad (7)$$

$$Precision = \frac{Tp}{Tp + Fp}; Recall = \frac{Tp}{Tp + Fn} \quad (8)$$

$$F_\beta - Score = (1 + \beta^2) \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{\beta \cdot Precision + Recall} \quad (9)$$

Where Tp, Tn, Fp and Fn mean the set of combinations between true-false and positive or negative cases in the confusion matrix. In the confusion matrix, the first class is defined by the minority class A, fishing ships.

Table 1. Accuracy results (Holdout|K-Fold)

Feature type	Model	Without B. [%]	RUS [%]	SMOTE [%]	WCE [%]
Static: Φ_1	Tree	71.07 83.27	52.30 82.25	76.80 79.03	-----
	CNN	75.85 84.90	75.34 79.74	73.73 79.52	79.80 74.45
Kinematic: Φ_2	LSTM	81.08 83.75	69.79 80.20	78.94 83.65	81,38 77.12
	CNN_T	83.16 85.26	81.34 89.53	82.31 80.96	80.23 80.22

Table 1 shows the results of the accuracy of the four classification models against the different balancing techniques used. On the other hand, the results obtained in the F-score are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. F₁-Score (Holdout|K-Fold)

Feature type	Model	Without B. [%]	RUS [%]	SMOTE [%]	WCE [%]
Static: Φ_1	Tree	66.59 72.71	35.71 72.48	70.30 74.19	-----
	CNN	74.62 73.97	64.85 78.25	74.76 77.75	68.86 75.50
Kinematic: Φ_2	LSTM	----- 68.70	71.68 80.84	69.72 68.71	73.48 74.78
	CNN_T	67.20 72.50	60.34 89.40	63.87 79.20	70.42 78.71

Fig. 5. Classifiers with different balancing techniques and validation strategies. Solid markers Holdout, solid edge without face color K-Fold. Edge and marker face color, {red, green, blue, cyan} = {Tree, CNN, LSTM and CNN Time}. Markers {circle, square, triangle and diamond} = {unbalanced, RUS, SMOTE, WCE}.

Table 2 shows a strong bias for LSTM in holdout validation strategy when it is does not apply a balancing technique. This model classifies the validation set as the majority class, obtaining a similar accuracy as the percentage data of the majority class, but a null F_1 -Score. The classifier with the highest accuracy in holdout and k-fold is CNN_T with unbalanced data and RUS respectively. For the F_1 -Score case the static CNN and CNN_T acquire the best results with a RUS. While in the case of holdout the classifier with the best accuracy and F_1 -Score relationship is the LSTM with WCE, these results are improved when K-Fold is used. Specifically, CNN_T with RUS shows significantly higher values than the other classifiers. WCE improves F_1 -Score in 83% of cases and improves the accuracy of CNN and LSTM using Holdout validation. In the case of the tree classification, WCE has not been applied, so in **Table 1** and **Table 2**, the results are shown with dashed lines. Using the accuracy and F_1 -Score variables shown in **Table 1** and **Table 2** as variables of an \mathbb{R}^2 space, it is obtain **Fig. 5**. This figure shows the distribution of the different classifiers whit holdout and K-Fold validation strategies on the evaluation space-plane. In **Fig. 5**, 90% of the classifiers appear clustered around 70-90% accuracy and 65-90 F_1 -Score, while 3 of the classifiers are positioned very far apart due to lack of accuracy, F_1 -Score or both. To differentiate between them, we zoom into the region of maximum classifier concentration.

5 Conclusions

This paper has presented two main approaches to automatically classify fishing ships from other vessels using trajectory information. The two approaches used are classical and DL. In addition, in the DL approach, two of the main trends in the literature, LSTM, and CNN neural networks, have been compared using panel and flattened data structure. The classifier clustering around the same region of the comparison plane suggests a similarity of the evaluation methods. However, applying K-Fold eliminates outliers in the classifiers, clustering the results to a greater extent than holdout on the comparison plane. The performance of the DL approximations is superior to the classification tree approximations. It has been shown that in the case of the CNN architecture the influence of the bias in the data is not as pronounced as in the LSTM, which is completely biased in classification. However, applying balancing techniques produces a considerable improvement, achieving the best accuracy-F-Score ratio applying WCE.

The successful results of CNN with both static and sequential kinematic data structures suggest that the convolutional layers are capable to extract hidden features from the trajectories. Furthermore, applying RUS in the training process has shown good results with CNNs, which may be a consequence of the decimation of large numbers of segments from the same complete trajectories. WCE has been shown to improve or at least equal results in the case of holdout validation, but with K-Fold cross-validation other strategies have been shown to be superior in the face of bias. For an ideal classifier, the evaluation with Holdout and K-fold should be equal, however, in **Table 1** and **Table 2** a lot of noise is observed in the RUS method. However, the proposed WCE method, with the CNN_T classifier has a 1% change between the two evaluation methods, so it is considered more stable than the rest of the proposed methods and classifiers. Although the general results show a superior performance of CNNs, the ability of LSTMs to work dynamically on non-fixed sequences of data or the possibility to deepen and

densify the presented structure or even hybridize it with convolutional layers shows great opportunities for problems such as this work. Finally, this paper provides a new approach to the vessel classification.

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